

The journey in search of truth that has brought us to the era of artificial intelligence.

How do we know what intelligence and truth are? It's a challenging question. For millennia, humans have been on the quest for "truth." Initially, it was thought of as something that could be determined from basic concepts of logic. Building on the idea that geometry and mathematics could describe the world essentially perfectly, while the version of the world we perceive is presented to us in a corrupt or undesirable form, ancient thinkers sought the truth in the foundations of mathematics. Their commitment to this idea was so strong that after Plato founded the "Ἀκαδημία" (academy), the entrance bore the inscription: "Let no one ignorant of geometry enter here." Many mathematicians began to think that it was possible to extend logic, which occurs as an inherently internal process of our minds, to other fields such as arithmetic, in a way that would provide a procedure for externalizing calculations. In other words, "mechanizing the truth." With this in mind, Ada Lovelace, the Countess of Lovelace, along with Charles Babbage (to a lesser extent), attempted to create algorithms that could be operated by a machine, becoming the world's first "programmers."

The major setback in the pursuit of "truth" was Gödel's proof, which demonstrated that "there are truths that cannot be proven." This was a cold shower for mathematics. Moreover, it's strangely paradoxical. For example, one can make the following statement and evaluate whether it's true or not:

this statement is not written

However, the content of the statement is contradictory because if it were not written, one could not have read it. Nevertheless, it can be considered a modified version:

"this statement is not written"

Simply using quotation marks indicates to our brains that this sentence may come from a different context. For example, something someone said, so the sentence written this way is true because it refers to a quote. In this sense, it refers to a context that we are ignorant of and cannot prove (the existence of that person and context). Therefore, one can assume as true things that cannot be proven.

While this was a blow to the logical foundations of mathematics, it could be "omitted" in a way. For instance, Alan Turing focused on the part of logic that could be proven. He mechanized the "provable" part of logic, laying the groundwork for the modern computer. In this line, Turing was deeply concerned with whether by mechanizing calculations, the machine he had created had the capacity to "think." This was revolutionary at the time, as other scientists, like John von Neumann, were more interested in using the new machine to solve problems like the equations of the atomic bomb. In other words, they were trying to use machines to solve equations and thus find or describe a portion of the world around us.

Despite this, there were some who held steadfast to Turing's ideas, even outside the realm of mathematics. Walter Pitts, for example, was a mathematician who made contributions to early

modern neuroscience, particularly in organizing the neurons in the brain using mathematical functions. Today, we know that this was the origin of what we now call artificial intelligence. Interestingly, both Turing and Pitts died tragically and without knowing the tremendous impact they had on the history of humanity.

Regarding the question of whether a machine can "think," Gödel had his own thoughts. He believes that what we have today is "mechanical intelligence in search of truth," where "learning" (deep learning) is essentially adding weights to a set of data. This is similar to how our brains work, where given a certain number of stimuli, our response will depend on how we value each of them. This leads to people seeing different things when looking at the same data, and when we have the same weights, we agree. The challenge with this system is that many think that computers truly "think," but it's clear that much more is needed to build an automatic version of ourselves that seeks the truth. Gödel believes that true artificial intelligence will be the one that "feels" the desire to do something, experiences curiosity about the world by itself, explores its innermost desires, and even suffers to survive. Only then could we truly talk about "artificial intelligence," and it's also at that point that the world could become a more terrifying place.

Patricio Venegas-Aravena

Department of Structural and Geotechnical Engineering, School of Engineering, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, Vicuña Mackenna 4860, Macul, Santiago, Chile. plvenegas@uc.cl.

References

Goles, E.: *Una Especie de Zumbido en la Cabeza: de la verdad matemática a la inteligencia artificial*. Planeta, ISBN: 9789563607949, 2020.